

Response to the Reviewers' Comments

“Augmented Latent Features of Deep Neural Network-Based Automatic Speech Recognition for Motor-Driven Robots”

Reference No: applsci-733724

General

We appreciate the valuable comments and suggestions of the reviewers on our paper very much. In our revised manuscript, we have incorporated almost all the comments and suggestions made by the reviewers, and have given additional explanations. Our detailed responses are as follows:

Response to Reviewer 1's Comments

1. The authors mention they use Cross-Entropy loss. This makes sense for senones and motor-state as targets, but I'm not sure I understand how this loss function can apply to MFCC. Shouldn't MSE Loss be used here?

⇒ We modified the manuscript such that

“The cross-entropy between the network output and target is minimized by using senones and motor-states as the labels, and the MSE loss is minimized to restore a clean version of MFCC.” (line 131-131)

2. Why is the vector for the motor-state 2-D? It seems like a 1-D binary value would do it.

⇒ The robot sends the motor-state information with two states (off and on) as a binary value, but it is one-hot encoded before being entered into the network. The first state, which considered only the fan noise, is represented by index 0 and encoded as [1, 0]. On the other hand, the second state represented by index 1 is encoded as [0, 1], considering both the fan and movement noise. These one-hot encoded inputs are delivered to the first DNN.

3. Can you explain why you have to concatenate the MFCC features with the bottleneck features for the second stage?

⇒ The primary DNN for describing the acoustic modeling receives the MFCC features corresponding to the acoustic information as the main input. In this paper, a latent feature designed to effectively represent the information about whether the motor is operating or not is used as an additional input. This is described in section 3.

“There seems to be a possibility that the acoustic modeling capabilities can be improved due to the additional input that more effectively represents the information about whether the motor is operating or not under the acoustic circumstances, which will be verified in detail in the following experimental section.” (line 138-141)

4. Have you considered training with multiple targets at the same time (e.g. senone, MS and MFCC) with some weighting?

⇒ We designed a relatively light model considering the embedded system. Therefore, in our experiments, some labels such as the clean MFCC features often yielded worse results, and the multiple labels could

also produce worse results. The multiple labels may be considered in future works along with the deeper models.

5. When training the auto encoder to predict the motor-state, why would the auto encoder store any information about the MFCC?
 - ⇒ In order to maximize the representation of the motor-state information under the acoustic circumstances, the latent features attempt to fuse the acoustic features and motor-state data.
6. In the experiments with TIMIT, the baseline performs similarly with motor on and off in terms of PER, whereas the experiments with LibriSpeech show that the baseline performs worse with the motor on compared to the motor off. I'm not sure I understand why TIMIT seems more "robust" to motor noise?
 - ⇒ TIMIT was excluded from this experiment because it is a small dataset and often shows unreliable results.

Response to Reviewer 2's Comments

1. I do not see a comparison with state-of-the-art methods
 - ⇒ To compare with other speech enhancement system, the results of the DNN-based spectral feature mapping were added in Tables 3, 4. Also we modified the section 1 (Introduction), which includes the DNN-based speech enhancement systems.

“In addition, the proposed model was superior to the spectral feature mapping, a DNN-based speech enhancement method. In this experiment, the DNN for the spectral feature mapping was designed lighter than the usual DNN-based mapping model to have a similar amount of computation as the proposed preliminary network, and did not bring a significant performance improvement.” (line 195-198)

“In general, DNN-based speech enhancement models are trained using two types of targets, including masking-based targets and mapping-based targets. In the first case, the models attempt to describe the time-frequency (T-F) relationships of clean speech to background interference and make a binary classification decision on T-F units, such as estimating the ideal binary mask [13]. Furthermore, In [14], DNNs were used to estimate a smoothed ideal ratio mask (IRM) in the Mel frequency domain for robust ASR. In the second case, the DNNs learn the complex mapping function from noisy to clean speech using multi-condition training data [19]. However, these conventional speech enhancements generally require large databases and very deep models to cope with as much ambient noises as possible, which is not suitable for the embedded systems such as the humanoid robots. In addition, these models have limitations in using motor-state information as an auxiliary feature.” (line 29-39)
2. As stated in line 177, the baseline neural network is stripped of fine-tuning techniques such as LDA. How do we know that the deterioration in PER is not due solely (or to an overwhelming degree) to the lack of this extra fine-tuning? In order to clearly show the effect of motor state bottleneck features, both baseline methods should have the same fine-tuning algorithms as the Kaldi implementations.; Line 142: What is the "development set"?; Line 152: There is no info about the testing set.
 - ⇒ Since TIMIT database is a small dataset and often shows unreliable results, it was excluded from this experiment.

3. More details should be provided on the LibriSpeech set test. For instance, how was ego-noise inserted?

⇒ We added and modified the sentences to explain the types of ego-noise and how the ego-noise was inserted into LibriSpeech database.

“These noise signals involve two types of the ego-noise including fan and movement noises. The first type of the ego-noise labeled “ Motor Off ” only considers the fan noise, while the second type labeled as “ Motor On” considers both the fan and movement noise. The mixing was conducted at various signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) levels including 5 dB and 15 dB with 1 m distance between the speaker and robot. These mixtures were then used to train and evaluate the ego-noise robust ASR algorithms described above. Our experiments were performed on the LibriSpeech database which is composed of three distinct training subsets of 100, 360, and 500 hours of speech respectively, representing a total training set of 960 hours of read English speech. In our experiments, we used 100 hours subset and further augmented the database via simulating the ego-noises that we recorded in reality. The waveform sampling rate of the corpus and the recorded noises was set to 16 kHz.” (line 148-158)

Response to Reviewer 3’s Comments

1. In the experimental analysis the only comparative method is [9] from the same authors. I think that other approaches should be considered, in particular some of the noise suppression approaches described in the introduction.; The state of the art describes some works on noise suppression but there is nothing on data augmentation which is where most of the improvement lie in ASR.

⇒ To compare with other speech enhancement system, the results of the DNN-based spectral feature mapping were added in Tables 3, 4. Also we modified the section 1 (Introduction), which includes the DNN-based speech enhancement systems.

“In addition, the proposed model was superior to the spectral feature mapping, a DNN-based speech enhancement method. In this experiment, the DNN for the spectral feature mapping was designed lighter than the usual DNN-based mapping model to have a similar amount of computation as the proposed preliminary network, and did not bring a significant performance improvement.” (line 195-198)

“In general, DNN-based speech enhancement models are trained using two types of targets, including masking-based targets and mapping-based targets. In the first case, the models attempt to describe the time-frequency (T-F) relationships of clean speech to background interference and make a binary classification decision on T-F units, such as estimating the ideal binary mask [13]. Furthermore, In [14], DNNs were used to estimate a smoothed ideal ratio mask (IRM) in the Mel frequency domain for robust ASR. In the second case, the DNNs learn the complex mapping function from noisy to clean speech using multi-condition training data [19]. However, these conventional speech enhancements generally require large databases and very deep models to cope with as much ambient noises as possible, which is not suitable for the embedded systems such as the humanoid robots. In addition, these models have limitations in using motor-state information as an auxiliary feature.” (line 29-39)

2. I do not understand what the bottleneck features describe about the acoustics. Basically the preliminary DNN is the acoustic model used in [9]. So, is it a sort of pre-training? Is it equivalent to adding layers to the AM?

The motivations provided by the Authors are rather vague. Are the different models trained in the same (or comparable) way? Is the AM architecture good enough?

⇒ When using senones as the target, the preliminary DNN is similar to the acoustic model used in [9], except that the bottleneck layer is added in this experiment. However, the roles of two networks are completely different. In [9], the DNN was used to account acoustic modeling and one-hot encoding was used to express the motor-state information. On the other hand, in this paper, in order to effectively represent the information about whether the motor is operating or not under the acoustic circumstances, the latent features are designed by fusing the motor-state information and the corresponding acoustic information at the preliminary DNN.

3. Clarify how far the baseline used for TIMIT is from the state-of-the-art. Typically, filter-banks with fmlr are used as features for ASR instead of MFCC. Also the AM architecture is far from the state-of-the-art on TIMIT. Report the WER on clean TIMIT to give an idea of how good the AM is. Note that improving over a bad baseline is useless. So this aspect is fundamental. If the proposed method works, it should help also in presence of a better AM.; The numbers are a bit strange. With motor-on PER is lower than with motor-off. In addition, at 20dB the proposed method is better than the clean condition. In my opinion the Author must consider a state-of-the-art acoustic modelling to see what are the actual benefits of the proposed method; Experiments on Librispeech are not described or discussed at all: what are clean and other in the tables? Is the AM the same used for TIMIT? The state-of-the-art on Librispeech is approx. 5% WER. This last experiment is totally useless if presented in the current form.

⇒ TIMIT was excluded from this experiment because it is a small dataset and often shows unreliable results.

4. I do not understand what are the SNRs in Table 3 and Table 4. If the motor is off in table 3, what noise is that?

⇒ We modified the manuscript such that

“These noise signals involve two types of the ego-noise including fan and movement noises. The first type of the ego-noise labeled “Motor Off” only considers the fan noise, while the second type labeled as “ Motor On” considers both the fan and movement noise.” (line 149-151)

5. Explain why different SNR are there. The ego-noise should be constant.

⇒ Depending on the position of the mechanical parts inside the robot, the SNR may be different even if the noise type is the same. Therefore, different SNRs were considered in this experiment.

6. Line 121: clarify better what are the labels. This sentence is not clear. It is clear only later that 3 different labels are used.

⇒ We modified the manuscript such that

“For training, three different targets are placed at the output, including senones, motor-state, and MFCC. The cross-entropy between the network output and target is minimized by using senones and motor-states as the labels, and the MSE loss is minimized to restore a clean version of MFCC.” (line 130-133)

7. Why are only 2 engine state considered? Typically the noise is different depending on what part is moving and how.

⇒ In this paper, a feasibility study was conducted to investigate the effect of latent features for efficiently

representing motor-state information. As we described in the manuscript, more diverse states of the robot could be considered in a future work.

“In a future work, more diverse states of the robot could be considered as the motor data, e.g. walking state, right/left arm rotating state, head shaking state, or multiple states” (line 215-217)